

Resin Membrane Electrodes for the Activity Measurements in Aquo Organic Media, Part I.

M. Adhikari and G. G. Biswas

Attempts have been made to prepare resin membrane electrodes suitable for measurement of anionic activities in aquo-organic media. Membranes made from Amberlite IRA 401, Amberlite IRA 400 and Dowex 1 × 8 resin perform well in comparison to Amberlite IR 45 resin and their performance in aquo-methanolic and aquo-ethanolic media are satisfactory in comparison to aquo-*n*-propanolic media. The range of molalities in which Nernst's equation is valid with these membranes is not more than ·027 for monovalent and ·0027 for divalent though in some cases exceptions are noted.

Determination of cation activity in aqueous solution with the help of membrane electrodes is an established fact.¹⁻³ The evaluation of cation activity with the help of clay membrane is also possible in aquo-organic media⁴.

Synthetic organic ion exchange resins have greater exchange capacities than clay minerals. It was expected that the ion-exchange resin membranes would be more suitable for evaluation of ion activity in aquo-organic media and attempt has been made to determine the cation and anion activities with resin membrane electrodes in aqueous and aquo-organic media. In the present paper determination of anion activity of mono and di-valent ions in aqueous and aquo-organic media is presented.

EXPERIMENTAL

(a) *Preparation of electrodes* : Resin membranes were prepared from mixture of finely powdered (200 mesh) anion exchange resin and similarly powdered polystyrene in the ratio of 3 : 7 and 4 : 6 respectively under an oil press in steel mould at an initial temp. of 130°–150° and an initial pressure of 4000 p.s.i. The prepared discs were cut into suitable sizes with the help of sharp blades and the membrane-electrodes were prepared by fixing the membranes at the end of glass tube of suitable size.

(b) *Choice of membranes* : A number of membrane electrodes were prepared by the above method and from stock ideal membranes were selected by trial. Those which gave reproducible theoretical result and having negligible asymmetry (± 0.1 mv) were taken to be ideal.

1. C. E. Marshall, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1939, **43**, 1155.
2. S. K. Sinha, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **31**, 577.
3. S. K. Bose, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 465.
4. M. Adhikari, *ibid.*, 1961, **38**, 817.

(c) *Electrical connection* : The connection was made with the help of tiny calomel electrodes. Any pair of electrodes showing an asymmetry potential greater than 0.1 mv. was rejected. The observed value of the e.m.f. for the cell of the type

would be

$$E = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_1}{a_2} \quad \text{where } a_1 > a_2.$$

The individual ion activity was calculated with the help of Debye-Hückel limiting equation. The dielectric values were evaluated graphically from the experimental data of G. Akerlof⁵ and the mean molecular weights of the media were taken to be equal to m_1x_1 , m_2x_2 where m_1 , m_2 and x_1 , x_2 are the molecular weights and the mole fractions of the solvent and the solute respectively.

(d) *Preparation of Calomel electrodes* : The salt bridge of the tiny calomel electrodes was prepared with the corresponding aquo-organic solvent by refluxing the thoroughly washed agar-agar, kch in the solvent. In the case of 60% aquo-organic mixture the ideality of the calomel electrode is destroyed earlier and calomel electrodes prepared by 40% organic solvent with water were used for measurement in 60% organo-aqueous system and in the case of aquo-propanolic media calomel electrodes made by 20% organic solvent with water were used as the preparation of calomel electrode with 40% and 60% propanol were not possible.

TABLE I

Characteristics of the membranes used

Resins	Matrix ionic groups	Exchange capacity	Thickness of membrane discs in mm.	Specific resistance in ohms.
Amerlite IRA 401	Polystyrene -N(alkyl) ₃	3 meq/g	0.651	$0.711 \times 10^4 - 1.605 \times 10^4$
Amberlite IRA 400	„	2.6 meq/g	0.6256	$1.17 \times 10^4 - 6.2 \times 10^4$
Dowex 1 × 8	„	2.1 meq/g	0.4536	$1.5 \times 10^4 - 4.3 \times 10^4$
Amberlite IR 45	Polystyrene weakly basic amino group.	5 meq/g	0.4683	$2.31 \times 10^4 - 5.3 \times 10^4$

Results of measurements of activity of Cl' , Br' , I' , NO'_3 , SO'_4 , $\text{S}_2\text{O}'_3$, CrO'_4 , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}'_7$ ions in aqueous and aquo-organic solvent of different compositions were recorded. Only e.m.f. values within 0.5 mv to theoretical values were considered and the range of activity measurements possible with these membranes are shown in the Tables.

TABLE II

Range of activity measurements of various ions at 25° in aqueous medium with different membrane electrodes

Membranes	Cl' ions	Br' ions	I' ions	NO'_3 ions
Amberlite IRA 401	.001—.027	.001—.027	.001—.027	.001—.027
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	-do-	.001—.027	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	-do-	-do-	.001—.003	.001—.003
Dowex 1 × 8	-do-	-do-	.001—.027	.001—.027

TABLE III

Range of activity measurements of various ions at 25° in aqueous medium with different membrane electrodes

Membranes	CrO'_4 ions	$\text{Cr}_2\text{O}'_7$ ions	$\text{S}_2\text{O}'_3$ ions	SO'_4 ions
Amberlite IRA 401	.000092—.0039	.00009—.0039	.00009—.0018	.00009—.0018
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	-do-	.00009—.0018	-do-	-do-
Dowex 1 × 8	-do-	.00009—.0039	.00009—.0039	-do-

Methyl alcohol and water medium

TABLE IV

Range of Cl' activity measurements in aquo-methanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% Methanol	40% Methanol	60% Methanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00095—.0214	.00095—.02	.00093—.0026
Dowex 1 × 8	-do-	-do-	-do-
Amberlite IRA 400	.00095—.0028	.00094—.0027	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	-do-	-do-	-do-

TABLE V

Range of Br' activity measurements in aquo-methanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% Methanol	40% Methanol	60% Methanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00095—.021	.00095—.02	.00093—.0072
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	-do-	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	-do-	-do-	.00093—.0026
Dowex 1 × 8	-do-	.00094—.02	-do-

TABLE VI

Range of I' activity measurement in aquo-methanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% Methanol	40% Methanol	60% Methanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00095—.021	.00094—.02	.0093—.0072
Amberlite IRA 400	.00095—.0079	.00094—.0027	Not suitable
Amberlite IR 45	.00095—.0028	Not suitable	-do-
Dowex 1 × 8	.00095—.021	.00094—.02	-do-

TABLE VII

Range of NO₃' activity measurement in aquo-methanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% Methanol	40% Methanol	60% Methanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00096—.021	.00094—.02	.00093—.0072
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	Not suitable	Not suitable
Amberlite IR 45	.00096—.0028	-do-	-do-
Dowex 1 × 8	.00096—.021	.00094—.02	.00093—.0072

TABLE VIII

Range of Cr₂O₇" activity measurement in aquo-methanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% Methanol	40% Methanol	60% Methanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00009—.0034	.000088—.00024	.000085—.0012
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	-do-	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	.00009—.00025	.00009—.00024	.000085—.00023
Dowex 1 × 8	.00009—.0016	.000088—.00024	-do-

TABLE IX

Range of CrO₄" activity measurements in aquo-methanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% Methanol	40% Methanol	60% Methanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00009—.0016	.000088—.00062	Not suitable
Amberlite IRA 400	.00009—.0033	.000088—.0027	.000085—.0012
Amberlite IR 45	-do-	-do-	-do-
Dowex 1 × 8	-do-	.000088—.00024	-do-

TABLE X

Range of $S_2O_3^{2-}$ activity measurements in aquo-methanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% Methanol	40% Methanol	60% Methanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00009—.0016	.000088—.00062	Not suitable
Amberlite IRA 400	.00009—.00067	-do-	.000085—.00056
Amberlite IR 45	-do-	Not suitable	Not suitable
Dowex 1 × 8	.00009—.0033	.000088—.0024	.000085—.00056

TABLE XI

Range of SO_4^{2-} activity measurements in aquo-methanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% Methanol	40% Methanol	60% Methanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00009—.00067	.000088—.00062	.000085—.00056
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	-do-	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	Not suitable	Not suitable	Not suitable
Dowex 1 × 8	.00009—.0016	.000088—.0014	.000085—.00056

Ethyl alcohol and water medium

TABLE XII

Range of Cl^- activity measurement in aquo-ethanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% Ethanol	40% Ethanol	60% Ethanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.0009—.021	.0009—.019	.0009—.00256
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	.00093—.019	.0009—.0026
Amberlite IR 45	-do-	-do-	-do-
Dowex 1 × 8	.00095—.021	.00090—.019	-do-

TABLE XIII

Range of Br^- activity measurement in aquo-ethanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% Ethanol	40% Ethanol	60% Ethanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00095—.021	.00093—.02	.00091—.0068
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	-do-	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	-do-	-do-	.00091—.0025
Dowex 1 × 8	-do-	-do-	.0009—.0068

TABLE XIV

Range of I' activity measurement in aquo-ethanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% Ethanol	40% Ethanol	60% Ethanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00095—.021	.00094—.020	.00091—.0026
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	-do-	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	.00095—.0027	.00095—.0027	. Not suitable
Dowex 1 × 8	.00095—.021	.00094—.02	.0009—.0068

TABLE XV

Range of NO₃ activity measurement in aquo-ethanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% Ethanol	40% Ethanol	60% Ethanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00095—.021	.00094—.019	.00091—.00256
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	-do-	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	.00095—.0027	.00094—.00269	-do-
Dowex 1 × 8	.00095—.021	.00094—.019	-do-

TABLE XVI

Range of SO₄ activity measurement in aquo-ethanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% Ethanol	40% Ethanol	60% Ethanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00009—.0016	.000087—.0013	.000082—.0009
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	-do-	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	-do-	-do-	.000082—.0005
Dowex 1 × 8	-do-	-do-	.000082—.0009

TABLE XVII

Range of Cr₂O₇ activity measurement in aquo-ethanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% Ethanol	40% Ethanol	60% Ethanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00009—.0032	.000087—.0023	.000082—.0014
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	-do-	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	.00009—.0016	.000087—.0013	.000082—.0005
Dowex 1 × 8	.00009—.0032	.000087—.0023	.000082—.0014

TABLE XVIII

Range of CrO_4^{2-} activity measurement in aquo-ethanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% Ethanol	40% Ethanol	60% Ethanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00009—.0032	.000087—.0023	.000082—.0014
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	-do-	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	-do-	-do-	-do-
Dowex 1 × 8	-do-	-do-	-do-

TABLE XIX

Range of $S_2O_3^{2-}$ activity measurements in aquo-ethanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% Ethanol	40% Ethanol	60% Ethanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00009—.0016	.000087—.0013	.000082—.0009
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	-do-	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	-do-	-do-	-do-
Dowex 1 × 8	-do-	-do-	-do-

n-Propanol and water mixture

TABLE XX

Range of Cl^- activity measurement in aquo-n-propanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% n-Propanol	40% n-Propanol	60% n-Propanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00095—.02	.00093—.018	.00089—.002
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	-do-	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	-do-	-do-	Not suitable
Dowex 1 × 8	-do-	-do-	.00089—.0024

TABLE XXI

Range of Br^- activity measurements in aquo-n-propanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% n-Propanol	40% n-Propanol	60% n-Propanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00095—.021	.00093—.018	.00089—.014
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	.00093—.0072	.00089—.006
Amberlite IR 45	-do-	.0009—.018	.00089—.014
Dowex 1 × 8	-do-	-do-	-do-

TABLE XXII

Range of I' activity measurements in aquo-normal propanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% <i>n</i> -propanol	40% <i>n</i> -propanol	60% <i>n</i> -propanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00095—.0027	.00093—.00265	Not suitable
Amberlite IRA 400	.00095—.008	.00093—.0072	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	.00095—.0027	.00093—.0027	-do-
Dowex 1 × 8	.00095—.008	.00093—.007	.00089—.006

TABLE XXIII

*Range of NO₃ activity measurements in aquo-*n*-propanolic media at 25° by various membranes*

Membranes	20% <i>n</i> -propanol	40% <i>n</i> -propanol	60% <i>n</i> -propanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.00095—.008	.00093—.007	.00089—.0063
Amberlite IRA 400	.00095—.02	.00093—.018	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	.00095—.0027	.00093—.0026	.00089—.0024
Dowex 1 × 8	.00095—.008	.00093—.007	.00089—.0063

TABLE XXIV

*Range of CrO₄ activity measurements in aquo-*n*-propanolic media at 25° by various membranes*

Membranes	20% <i>n</i> -propanol	40% <i>n</i> -propanol	60% <i>n</i> -propanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.000089—.0015	.000085—.0012	.000077—.00071
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	-do-	.000077—.00042
Amberlite IR 45	-do-	-do-	-do-
Dowex 1 × 8	-do-	.000085—.0006	-do-

TABLE XXV

*Range of Cr₂O₇ activity measurements in aquo-*n*-propanolic media at 25° by various membranes*

Membranes	20% <i>n</i> -propanol	40% <i>n</i> -propanol	60% <i>n</i> -propanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.000089—.003	.000085—.0012	.000077—.00042
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	-do-	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	.000089—.0015	-do-	Not suitable
Dowex 1 × 8	.000089—.003	-do-	.000077—.0004

TABLE XXVI

Range of $S_2O_3^{2-}$ activity measurements in aquo-propanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% n-propanol	40% n-propanol	60% n-propanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.000089—.0015	.000085—.0012	.000077—.00071
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	-do-	.000077—.00042
Amberlite IR 45	-do-	-do-	.000077—.0008
Dowex 1 × 8	.000089—.003	.000085—.0019	-do-

TABLE XXVII

Range of SO_4^{2-} activity measurements in aquo-propanolic media at 25° by various membranes

Membranes	20% n-propanol	40% n-propanol	60% n-propanol
Amberlite IRA 401	.000089—.0015	.000085—.0012	.000077—.00042
Amberlite IRA 400	-do-	-do-	-do-
Amberlite IR 45	-do-	-do-	.000077—.0007
Dowex 1 × 8	-do-	-do-	.000077—.0008

DISCUSSION

Only those membranes which showed theoretical Nernst's value in the aqueous medium up to the activity range of .027 for monovalent and .0018 for divalent were used in aquo-organic media.

Experimental results as given in tables indicate clearly that these membranes behaving well in the aquo media were suitable also for aquo organic media and reproducible Nernst's value of e.m.f. could be obtained for monovalent ions within an accuracy of ± 0.05 m.v. With divalent ions the results were not so encouraging and the uncertainty in e.m.f. values were more than ± 0.05 m.v. for divalent ions in 60% aquo-organic media. It was observed that in 60% aquo-organic media the resistance of the media at lower electrolytic concentration was so high that reliable e.m.f. values were difficult to ascertain, which might be due to low dielectric constants of this media.

However the membranes made from Amberlite IRA 401 and Dowex 1 × 8 responded quite satisfactorily and comparatively reliable e.m.f. values could be recorded with such membranes in these media. The range of activities measurable in aquo-methanol, aquo-ethanol and aquo-propanol media for monovalent ions like Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- and for divalent ions like $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$, CrO_4^{2-} , $S_2O_3^{2-}$ and SO_4^{2-} are shown in the tables. It was observed that in most cases the Nernst's e.m.f. values could be obtained after a certain lapse of time with these electrodes in the dilute range but with gradual increase in the ionic concentration of the media the theoretical e.m.f. values differ widely from observed data, although the equilibrium between the membranes and the electrolyte in the solution were immediately established in concentrated range.

For activity measurements of CrO_4^{2-} , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and I^- solutions, the membranes were to be made reversible by exchanging the membranes in a very dilute solution e.g., $\approx 0.1\text{M}$, otherwise there would be deposition of these salts in the membrane surface and with iodide solution a deposition of elemental iodine would occur resulting increase in resistance during e.m.f. measurements and also there was uncertainty in e.m.f. values.

With Amberlite IR 45 membranes positive e.m.f. values in aqueous and aquo-organic media were obtained for monovalent ions, but the sign of e.m.f. changed in aqueous and aquo organic media for divalent ions like CrO_4^{2-} , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$, $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ and also in aquo organic medium for SO_4^{2-} . Similar reversal of sign of e.m.f. with membrane electrodes was reported earlier⁶ in activity measurements of some cations.

This type of behaviour of IR 45 may be explained on structural basis. The resin Amberlite IRA 400, IRA 401 and Dowex 1×8 contains strongly basic quaternary ammonium groups whereas the resin IR 45 is a poly functional weakly basic resins with primary, secondary and tertiary amino groups⁷. The pronounced ionic selectivity of Amberlite IRA 401, Amberlite IRA 400 and Dowex 1×8 is attributed to the fact that the quaternary ammonium groups retain substantially their degree of dissociation regardless of the change of the dielectric constant of the media. The weak basic groups of Amberlite IR 45 were less active electrochemically due to the decrease of the dielectric constant of the media as is the case with aquo-organic media. Even these weak basic groups are less active in aqueous medium for ions like $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$, CrO_4^{2-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ and the interaction between the anions of strong electrolyte and weakly basic amino groups of the membrane materials result in the development of negative charge on the membranes and thus behave as a cation exchanger. In the case of monovalent ions the reversal phenomena were not observed possibly due to difficulty in negative charge transfer on the membrane surface.

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Applied Chemistry Dept.,
Calcutta University.

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6. A. V. Grodivski, E. L. Phillipov, V. S. Sterman and D.I. Mendeleev, *Cf. Chem. Abs.*, **67**, 172318, p. 1631.
7. Helfferich, *Ion Exchange*, McGraw-Hill, 54, 1962.